

THE EFFECT OF INTERNAL LINER ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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SUMMARY: The main goal of this research is the study of the effect of the sealing liner on displacement and stress fields of a composite cylinder. The composite shell is made of Aramid fibers and epoxy resin using filament winding method and the internal liner is made of steel. The displacement and stress fields for the composite capsule with and without the internal liner are analyzed by the finite element methods. By using four different methods, the internal liner is modeled. All four methods present nearly similar results for the displacement and stress fields. Results obtained from the analysis show that the internal liner has an important effect on displacement and stress fields.

In this study the mechanical behavior of the metallic liner is assumed to be linearly elastic. Therefore in modeling process, the internal pressure is increased to such level which the liner material does not pass the elastic limit. In an ongoing study the elasto-plastic behavior of the internal liner is under research and the results will be published in a near future.

KEYWORDS: pressure vessel, internal metallic liner, design, finite element.

INTRODUCTION

A composite pressure vessel is an important example of applications of composite materials in industries. In design of composite pressure vessels, to simplify the analysis, the internal liner is not considered. The internal liner prevents from the leakage of the internal pressure and corrosion. However, it can be expected that the internal liner can influence the stress field in composites layer. In this research the effect of the internal liner on the stress and displacement fields of composite pressure vessels are studied.

By considering the complexity of the analysis of stress field, Nisa, finite element software is utilized. The composite pressure vessel is made by filament winding method. Epoxy resin and Aramid fibers are used as the matrix and reinforcement. The internal liner is made of stainless steel.

The geometry and the size of the pressure vessel is shown in the following figure, the internal pressure is equal to 25 bar.

Fig. 1 Geometry of the composite pressure vessel

The mechanical properties of the composite material is,

$$E_x = 90. \quad \text{GPa}$$

$$E_y = 4.1 \quad \text{GPa}$$

$$G_{xy} = 1.8 \quad \text{GPa}$$

$$\nu_{xy} = .28$$

and the mechanical properties of the metallic internal liner is,

$$E = 204. \quad \text{GPa}$$

$$\sigma_y = 600 \quad \text{MPa}$$

$$\sigma_u = 750. \quad \text{MPa}$$

$$\nu = .3$$

$$\epsilon_f = 40\%$$

FIBER ORIENTATION

The pressure vessel studied in this research consists of thirteen layers. There are two sets of fiber orientation, helical and spiral. On both ends of the vessel, because of the sliding of fibers during the manufacturing process, fibers in spiral direction do not exist. The fibers are oriented in $\pm 19^\circ$ in six layers and for the other seven layers the fibers are oriented in 90° with respect to the x-axis (Fig. 1). Therefore, the configuration of layers for the cylindrical part and the cap of the pressure vessel from outer to the inner surface can be shown by $[(19)_2/....]$, and $[(\pm 19)_6]$, respectively.

The thickness of each 90° layer is equal to 0.34 mm and the thickness of each $+19^\circ$ or -19° layer is equal to 0.32 mm. These thicknesses are measured experimentally. The total thickness in the cylindrical and the cap region without considering the thickness of the liner are equal to 4.3 mm and 1.92 mm, respectively. The liner is made of steel (Din 321), with the thickness of 0.33 mm.

ANALYSIS OF THE MODEL WITHOUT LINER

The finite element model of the pressure vessel is made by rotating of a section of that along x-axis (Fig. 1). The element used for stress analysis is the three dimensional composite shell element. By considering the symmetry of the model with respect to the middle of that, half of the vessel is modeled. A convergence analysis is performed to select the proper size of the elements.

In Fig. 2 the deformed geometry of the vessel is shown after loading. It must be mentioned that the maximum deflection is equal to 0.868 mm which happens in closed end area, i.e., for the cap of the vessel.

Fig. 2 Deformed geometry of the vessel after loading

Stress Distribution for the Model without Liner

In this section the stresses due to the internal pressure in composite layers of the vessel without considering the internal metallic liner are studied. The results obtained in this section will be compared with the results for the vessel with internal liner in the next section.

The stress in fiber direction σ_{xx} , the stress in matrix direction σ_{yy} and the in-plane shear stress σ_{xy} are studied. By considering two types of ply configurations in cylindrical and cap sections, stresses in these two sections are studied separately. In other words, stresses in helical and spiral directions are presented separately.

Stress Distribution in Helical Layers

As shown in Fig. 3, by considering the distribution of s_{xx} stress from the first layer (outer layers) to the last layer (inner layer), it is noted that around the intersection between cylindrical and the cap areas the σ_{xx} in the first layer decreases. By entering to the cap area ($x > 320$ mm) σ_{xx} is reached to zero and again increases to the maximum magnitude. For the lower layers, e.g., layer #7, as shown in Fig. 3, the rate of variation of σ_{xx} along x-axis is not great as that of the first layer. Then, internal layers, i.e., layers #12 and 13 have the maximum magnitude of s_{xx} in the area of where the first layer has the minimum magnitude. By entering to the cap area the s_{xx} stress decreases.

Fig. 3 Distribution of s_{xx} in helical layers for the model without liner

By considering the stress distribution for the aforementioned layers, it can be concluded that there is a bending in the region of interface between the cylindrical and cap regions. As shown in Fig. 3, the layer #1 is under compression in the mentioned area while the middle layers, e.g., layer #8 is near to neutral area, and the internal layers under tensile stresses. By looking at the deformed geometry of the vessel (Fig. 2), the bending in the region between cylindrical and cap regions can be observed.

Fig. 4 Distribution of s_{yy} in helical layers for the model without liner

It can be mentioned that in the cylindrical part of the vessel, near to the cap region, external and internal layers are under compressive and tensile stresses, respectively. It means that there is a bending in that region. By entering in to the cap region at a certain point ($x = ***$ mm) the

direction of the bending changes. At that point all curves have the same magnitudes. In other words, the magnitude of the stresses in all layers are the same. Therefore, there is no bending in that region. Then by passing through this region and entering to the cap area, external and internal layers are under tension and compression, respectively. Figs 4 and 5 show the distribution of the transverse and shear stresses. As shown in Figs 4 and 5, magnitudes of these stresses are nearly the same for all layers.

Fig. 5 Distribution of s_{xy} in helical layers for the model without liner

Stress Distribution in Spiral Layers

After studying the stresses in helical layers, the stresses in spiral layers are considered. The stress distribution show that the magnitude of stresses in adjacent layers are nearly the same. Therefore, four of seven hoop layers, i.e., layers #3, 5, 9, and 11 are discussed in this section. The results show that the shear stress s_{xy} in hoop layers is negligible. Therefore, this stress is not discussed in this section. It should be mentioned that the spiral layers are used in cylindrical section and fibers are winded at 90o angle with respect to the x-axis (axis of rotation). So, it is obvious that the shear stress is negligible for these layers. By considering Fig. 6 it is clear that the s_{xx} (stress in fiber direction has same magnitude for all layers, from the middle of the capsule up to the adjacent area between cylindrical and cap sections of the vessel. By entering to the cap region a drop in the magnitude of this stress is observed for all layers which is due to bending phenomenon in this region, discucced earlier. Again, the amount of the this stress increases up to a certain limit and after that a second drop in the magnitude of this stress is observed. By noting that in the cap area, there is no any hoop layer, then the magnitude of s_{xx} stress goes back to zero after $x = ***$ mm.

Fig. 6 Distribution of s_{xx} in spiral layers for the model without liner

The distribution of stresses normal to the fiber direction (matrix direction) for spiral layers is shown in Fig. 7. The layers #3 and 11 are the outer and inner layers, respectively. So, by considering the bending in the adjacent region of cylindrical and cap sections, it is obvious that the inner layers are under higher tensile stresses.

Fig. 7 Distribution of s_{yy} in spiral layers for the model without liner

ANALYSIS OF THE MODEL WITH LINEAR

In the literature, it is normally mentioned by different authors that the thin liner is responsible for the preventing from leakage and corrosion. Moreover, it is mentioned that this layer has no great effect on the strength of the pressure vessel. Therefore the internal liner is normally is not considered in the analysis by many investigators.

In this section it is intended to consider the effect of the liner on the stress distribution in the composite layers. The internal liner is modeled by different techniques and the results of analysis are compared with the results obtained in the previous section for the model without liner.

Modeling of the Composite Vessel with Internal Metallic Liner

Physically, the internal liner is in contact with the composite layer. This physical behavior can be modeled by different approaches. In this study, by using four different methods the composite pressure vessel with internal metallic liner is modeled and analyzed. The four different methods are explained in details in the following sections.

Fourteen-Layer Composites Model

In this model, the three-dimensional thin shell elements are used. The number of layer is fourteen, which thirteen of these layers are made of composite material and the internal layer is made of steel.

Merged Model

This model is made by creating two separate layers . One layer made of composite materials and the other is made of steel. Then the corresponding nodes are merged together to have the same displacement.

Coupled Displacement Model

The mesh generation of this model is exactly the same as the merged model, however the displacement of the conjugate nodes are coupled together. It means that the displacement of nodes of the elements of the internal layers are coupled to those of the external layers. Therefore, the load can be transferred from the internal to the external layer.

Gap Element Model

This model is also made by creating two separate layers . One layer made of composite materials and the other is made of steel. Also, another type of element called three dimensional gap element is used. The role of the gap element is to transfer the displacement and load from the nodes of the elements of the internal layers to those of the external layers. The gap element can transfer the displacement and load along its axis from one node to another.

The results obtained from all this four different methods are very similar to each other and show that the simulation of the physical beaver is performed successfully and each of these methods can be used for modeling purposes.

Comparison of the Displacement Fields of the Models with and without liner

In this section a comparison between the displacement fields of the models with and without internal metallic liner is presented. As shown in Fig. 8, a considerable difference exists between the results obtained from the model with and without internal liner. By comparing the results, it can be concluded that the internal liner has an extensive effect on decreasing the displacement of the composite layers under internal pressure. As shown in Fig. 8, the maximum displacement occurs at the interface between the gap and cylindrical regions ($x=350$ mm) for all models. The maximum deflection for the model without the internal liner is about 0.82 mm and for the other models (models with internal liner) the maximum magnitude of the displacement is about 0.13 mm. By considering these results, it can be concluded that ignoring the internal liner in design of composite pressure vessels is not a wise decision for simplification of design process and can lead to wrong results.

Fig. 8 Node displacements for the model with and without liner

Comparison of the Stress Fields of the Models with and without Liner

In this section the stress in fiber direction (s_{xx}), matrix direction (s_{yy}) and the shear stress (s_{xy}) for the models with and without internal liners are compared and discussed in detail. The stresses in helical and spiral layers are presented and compared separately.

Stresses in Helical Layers

By considering the results obtained in the previous section, it can be concluded that a considerable reduction in the magnitude of stresses must be encountered in the composite layers for the models with liner. Fig. 9 shows a maximum reduction of 70% in the magnitude of the stress in the fiber direction for the helical layers of the models with internal liner in comparison with the results obtained from the model without the liner.

It should be mentioned here, that the extensive effect of internal liner in reducing the amount of stresses in the composite layer is valid for the region in which the liner behaves linearly elastic. However, this effect can be predicted that must be somehow different for the region in which the liner behaves elasto-plastic. In an ongoing research by the author this topic is under study and the results will be published elsewhere.

Fig. 9 Distribution of s_{xx} for the helical layer of the models with and without liner

By considering the results obtained, it can be easily concluded that considering the internal liner in the finite element model can reduce the other stresses as well. This can be observed in Fig. 10 which show the distribution of the stress in matrix direction (s_{yy}) for the helical layer. As shown in Fig. 10, the maximum amount of stress in matrix direction for the model without liner is about 80 MPa and occurs at the end of the cap region, i.e., on the nipple area. While, the magnitude of

this stress for the models with the internal liner is about 10 MPa which show the extensive effect of the internal liner in modeling process.

Fig. 10 Distribution of s_{yy} for the helical layer of the models with and without liner

The effect of the internal liner in reduction of the shear stress s_{xy} is shown in Fig. 11. Again, the result show that ignoring the internal liner leads to considerable amount of error in analysis.

Fig. 11 Distribution of s_{xy} for the helical layer of the models with and without liner

Stresses in Spiral Layers

In this section the stress in fiber direction (s_{xx}) for the spiral composite layer (layer #3) of the models with and without liner are presented and compared. In Fig. 12 the distribution of this stress for different models is shown.

Fig. 12 Distribution of s_{xx} for the spiral layer of the models with and without liner

As shown in Fig. 12, considering the internal liner in the modeling decreases the maximum s_{xx} stress by amount of 25%. This result shows that the internal liner is also effective for decreasing the stresses in the spiral layers as well as the helical layers. Due to space limitation, the results of stress analysis for the stresses in the matrix direction (s_{yy}) is not presented here. However, the results show the this stress (s_{yy}) decreased by amount of 35%. It is obvious that the shear stress (s_{xy}) is negligible in spiral layer, and so is not discussed in here.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained from the analysis of the models of a composite pressure vessels with and without internal metallic liner proved that considering the internal layer has an extensive effect in reducing the displacement and stress fields. Using four different modeling techniques, the internal liner inside a composite pressure vessels is modeled successfully. All four different models present nearly similar results for the displacement and stress fields. It is important to note that the mechanical behavior of the metallic liner is assumed to be linearly-elastic. Therefore the results obtained in this study is valid for the pressure range which the stress in the internal liner remains below the elastic limit. To model the elasto-plastic behavior of the internal liner of the effect of that on the stress state of the composite layer a research is conducted by the author and the results will be published elsewhere. Therefore, in this research the main goal is to study the effect of the elastic metallic liner on the displacement and stress fields of a composite pressure vessel.

The results obtained in this study show that considering the internal liner in analysis has an extensive effect on reducing of displacement of stresses in composite layers. This show that ignoring the internal layer can lead to wrong results in design process. Although, ignoring the effect of internal liner by designer leads to design of a vessel with a higher safety factor, however

in a modern design philosophy, weight saving is a priority which can not be achieved in that way. So the results obtained in this research strongly suggest to consider the internal liner in design process to obtain an optimum design.

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